

Diethyldithiocarbamate as a Spectrophotometric Reagent for Determination of Vanadium

S. P. ARYA¹ and KAMINI ARORA

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University,
Kurukshetra-132 119

*Manuscript received 2 January 1990, revised 23 July 1990,
accepted 8 February 1991*

DIETHYLDITHIOCARBAMATE finds applications as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of many elements and for effecting many useful separations. Vanadium(v)¹ also reacts with diethyldithiocarbamate but its determination based on this reaction lacks selectivity which, however, can be enhanced by the change of its oxidation state. Accordingly, vanadium(v) is reduced to vanadium(III) by sodium dithionite and complexed with diethyldithiocarbamate. A spectrophotometric method for the determination of vanadium is presented here after extracting vanadium(III)-diethyldithiocarbamate complex into chloroform.

Experimental

A stock solution of vanadium (5 mg ml^{-1}) was prepared from sodium metavanadate and standardised titrimetrically² and diluted to give a standard solution containing $100 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of vanadium. Solutions of other elements were prepared by dissolving suitable salts in water or dilute hydrochloric acid. An aqueous solution of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (DDC; 1%, w/v) was prepared. Sodium dithionite and chloroform were used as reductant and extractant respectively. Absorbance measurements were made on a GS 5700 spectrophotometer.

To the sample solution (pH 6–12) containing vanadium ($\leq 125 \mu\text{g}$), sodium dithionite (200 mg) and enough distilled water were added to make the aqueous phase volume to 16 ml. The mixture was gently shaken for 1 min and after reduction of vanadium(v) to vanadium(III), the reagent solution (4 ml) was added. The yellow coloured complex was extracted with chloroform (10 ml) for 1 min. The extracted phase was transferred, anhydrous sodium sulphate was added to it for removing traces of water and the volume was made upto 10 ml with chloroform. The absorbance of the complex was measured at 395 nm against a reagent blank (which shows absorbance of 0.06 against chloroform).

Results and Discussion

Vanadium(III) is readily obtained by reducing vanadium(V) solution with dithionite³ which forms a yellow coloured complex with Na-DDC. The V^{III}-DDC complex can be quantitatively extracted into chloroform. The blank absorbs at 350 nm which decreases slowly and the absorption becomes negligible at 390 nm and beyond. The complex shows an absorption maximum at 390–395 nm which is chosen for the measurement.

The extraction of V^{III}-DDC complex into n-butanol is almost negligible. The complex is extracted partially (% extraction is shown in parenthesis) into dichloromethane (14), n-hexane (19), isoamyl alcohol (32) and methyl isobutyl ketone (37), but the extraction is high in ethyl acetate (74), isoamyl acetate (79), carbon tetrachloride (84), benzene (84) and chloroform (98). The absorbance is maximum in chloroform, so it was used as the extractant.

In the study of different variables, a 20 ml of aqueous phase containing 100 µg V/20 ml was extracted with 10 ml of chloroform and the absorbance was measured at 395 nm. The optimum conditions for maximum absorbance are : 0.1–1.5 g of sodium dithionite, 4–8 ml of DDC solution, 0.5–10 min equilibration time, 1 min shaking time for reduction and 10 ml of chloroform for single extraction.

The yellow coloured complex of vanadium follows Beer's law in the range of 0.8–12.5 µg V/ml with a Sandell sensitivity of 0.012 µg V/cm². The complex is stable at least for 20 min. Single extraction with 10 ml of chloroform removes more than 98% of vanadium. The molar ratio of vanadium to diethyldithiocarbamate in the extracted complex found by Job's method of continuous variations is 1 : 3.

The effect of foreign ions was studied in the determination of vanadium (20 µg ml⁻¹). 500 mg each of sodium acetate, sodium sulphate, sodium chloride and thiourea ; 100 mg of sulphosalicylic acid ; 20 mg each of sodium tartrate, sodium pyrophosphate and sodium thioglycollate ; 10 mg of sodium cyanide and 5 mg of *o*-phenanthroline were found to have no effect on the absorbance of the complex. However, EDTA, potassium citrate and sodium oxalate (≥20 mg of each) interfere seriously. Iron(III) and manganese(II) give brown coloured extracts under the condition. However, limited amounts of these ions can be tolerated by the addition of *o*-phenanthroline to the aqueous solution after reduction with sodium dithionite. The interference of Fe, Cu and Pb when present in larger amounts, can be overcome by pre-extraction of their diethyldithiocarbamates with chloroform at pH 8.5–9.0. Co^{II} and Ni^{II} give green extracts but in the presence of sodium cyanide their extraction can be inhibited. Hydrolysable ions such as Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, Sn^{II} and Sb^V are not extracted but their tolerance limits are lowered due to their tendency to cause emulsion formation on shaking with chloroform. Pb^{II} and Tl^I cause 10% enhancement in

absorbance of the complex, so they are little tolerated. Bi^{III}, Ag^I and Ti^{IV} interfere by giving coloured extracts ranging from light yellow to brown. The tolerance limits of various cations are : 5 mg each of Ce^{IV}, Th^{IV}, Zr^{IV}, Hg^{II}, Cd^{II}, Pb^{II} ; 2 mg each of Zn^{II}, Al^{III}, As^V ; 1 mg each of Sn^{II}, Sb^V, W^{VI} ; 0.5 mg each of Cr^{VI}, U^{VI}, Co^{II} ; 0.2 mg each of Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Mo^{VI} and 0.1 mg of Ni^{II}.

The applicability of the method was tested by the satisfactory analysis of a variety of synthetic samples and a carbon-steel sample. In the analysis of carbon-steel sample, the excess iron is first removed by extracting its diethyldithiocarbamate complex into chloroform at pH 8.5–9.0 and then an aliquot of the sample solution was analysed by the proposed method.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. D. M. Puri, Chairman, Chemistry Department, Kurukshetra University, for facilities.

References

1. J. KORKISCH, "Modern Methods for the Separation of Rarer Metal Ions", Pergamon, Oxford, 1969, p. 449.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "A Textbook of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Longman, London, 1961, p. 309.
3. V. YATIRAJAM and S. P. ARYA, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1976, **86**, 208.